

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION STUDIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The aim of the article is to identify and analyze the challenges and obstacles in higher education. By exploring these issues in-depth, the article aims to identify limitations within translation studies and language proficiency development. Translation studies in higher education face a large number of challenges. They impact the readiness of students for professional translation industry. This thesis explains the key problems encountered in translation studies programs at the university degree and proposes innovative solutions to address these challenges. Overall, the issues within translation studies in higher education, the key problems include lack of practical experience, limited exposure to industry tools technology and cultural understanding. By addressing these issues comprehensively through practical training, integration of modern technologies in higher education can evolve to better equip students for successful careers in the field of translation.*

Keywords: Higher education, practice, technology, translation, challenges, machine, study, factors.

Аннотация. *Цель статьи – выявить и проанализировать проблемы и препятствия в сфере высшего образования. Путем углубленного изучения этих вопросов статья направлена на устранение ограничений в области переводческих исследований и развития языковых навыков. Переводческие исследования в сфере высшего образования сталкиваются с большим количеством проблем. Они влияют на готовность студентов к профессиональному переводу. В этой диссертации объясняются ключевые проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются программы изучения перевода на университетском уровне, и предлагаются инновационные решения для решения этих проблем. В целом, ключевые проблемы переводческих исследований в сфере высшего образования включают отсутствие практического опыта, ограниченное знакомство с отраслевыми технологиями и культурным пониманием. Комплексно решая эти вопросы посредством практического обучения, интеграция современных технологий в высшее образование может развиваться, чтобы лучше подготовить студентов к успешной карьере в области перевода.*

Ключевые слова: Высшее образование, практика, технологии, перевод, проблемы, машина, учеба, факторы.

Annotatsiya. *Bu maqola asosan oliy ta'limdagi muammo va qiyinchiliklarni yoritib beradim. Ushbu masalalar chuqur o'rganiladi, tarjimashunoslik va til bilish darajasini rivojlantirish doirasidagi cheklanishlarni yoritiladi. Oliy ta'limdagi tarjimashunoslik ko'plab muammolarga duch kelmoqda. Bu omillar talabalarning professional tarjima sohasidagi tayyorgarligiga o'z ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Bu ilmiy ishda universitetning tarjimashunoslik dasturlarida duch keladigan asosiy muammolarni yoritib beradi va ushbu muammolarni hal qilish uchun yechimlarni taklif qiladi. Umumiy olganda, oliy ta'limda tarjimashunoslik bilan bog'liq muommolar, asosiy muommolar asosan amaliy tajribaning yetishmasligi, kerakli mexanizmlar texnologiyalar cheklangan va madaniy tushunchalarni o'z ichiga oladi. Shunga o'xshash masalalarni amaliy mashg'ulotlar orqali bartaraf etish mumkin. Shuningdek, oliy ta'limga zamonaviy texnologiyalarni integratsiyalash orqali ham talabalar tarjima orqali talabalarni*

tarjima sohasida muvaffaqiyatli kasb egallashlari uchun zarur bo'lgan texnologiya bilan ta'mishlash lozim.

Kalit so'zlar: Oliy ta'lim, amaliyot, texnologiya, tarjima, muammolar, mashina, o'qish, omillar.

Introduction

Recognizing the difficulties encountered in teaching translation studies at universities is key to enhancing the education provided in this area. Factors such as different cultures and languages, advancements in technology, ethical questions, diverse teaching methods, and the globalized environment all make learning and teaching translation complex. By studying these problems, we can create better ways to educate future translators and meet the needs of today's translation industry. This thesis examines these challenges to show how universities can prepare students more effectively for successful careers in translation in our interconnected world.

Literature review

Global translation market has grown rapidly in the past 20 years and puts the current growth rate at between 5 and 7.5% per year. A longer constant increase can be found in the Index Translationum since 1932 (under the auspices of UNESCO since 1948, computerized since 1979). There are more than 5,000 intergovernmental organizations operative in today's world (see the annual Yearbook of International Organizations); most of them adopt some kind of bilingual or multilingual policy, if only to please the governments. In higher education, there are various challenges related to the field of translation studies. Some of the key issues include:

- Translating texts across cultures requires a deep understanding each language and its cultural context. Provide for the intended meaning and tone of the original text while adapting it to a different cultural setting as a complex task.

- While technology has escalated translation processes through machine translation tools and software, the accuracy and quality of machine translations still fall short of human translation in capturing and cultural subtleties of language.

- Creating uniform standards and criteria for translation quality and professionalism of the field. Training programs for translators need to include address emerging challenges and equip translators with the necessary skills in a rapidly changing linguistic landscape.

- Cost constraints and time pressures in the translation industry can compromise the quality of translations. Stabilizing efficiency with accuracy and ensuring fair compensation for translators are in progress challenges in the sward.

Addressing these challenges requires cooperation between students to ensure that translation studies programs in higher education remain relevant, rigorous and effective in preparing future translators.

Lawrence Venuti opinion about translation studies: As a translation theorist, Venuti has emphasized the importance of cultural aspects in translation, underscoring the need for a strong focus on cultural understanding within translation studies curricula.

The American philosopher and linguist Noam Chomsky once famously said: "A language is not just words. It's a culture, a tradition, a unification of a community, a whole history that creates what a community is. It's all embodied in a language." Although these terms hold great significance for language professionals, the continuous efforts over the years to automate translation imply that the tech industry is optimistic about translation the near future.

Method

To address in translation studies programs in higher education, a comprehensive approach is needed. Here are some methods to improve translation studies:

- Collaborating with translation agencies, companies or professional organizations.
- They need practical training: Providing hands-on training with real-world translation projects or internship.
- Teaching students how to adopt ti new technologies and stay updated with industries.
- Offering joint programs with other departments such as business, law or healthcare for specialized translation skills.

By implementing these methods, translation studies programs can overcome challenges in higher education, better prepare students for the demands of the translation industry Nd ensure the quality of their educational offerings.

Results and discussion

The research conducted on the challenges within translation studies in higher education has highlighted substantial obstacles that require urgent attention within the academic sphere.

- The investigation has highlighted a critical issue regarding the lack of sufficient practical training opportunities in translation studies programs. This limitation restricts students from obtaining the essential hands-on experience required to hone their translation skills.

- A significant problem is the lack of using specific tools and software in the curriculum, which stops students from learning important technology skills for translation.

- The research shows that translation programs don't focus enough on cultural understanding, making it hard for students to create culturally sensitive and accurate translations.

It is crucial to work on these challenges to make translation programs in universities more effective. Ways to improve might include:

- Improving by doing more hands-on activities like internships, workshops, and real translation projects can help students gain practical skills and real-world experience.

- By putting more emphasis on cultural studies in translation programs, students can better grasp different cultural backgrounds, leading to more accurate and high-quality translations.

- Teaching students how to use industry tools and software in their studies can help them learn the tech skills they need for today's translation work.

- Universities can improve their translation programs by using these methods, helping students be more ready for the varied challenges of the translation field and connecting academic learning with real-world industry needs.

Conclusion

In short, the difficulties in translation studies within higher education are varied and need thorough attention. Cultural and language diversity, technological progress, ethical issues, teaching methods, and the influence of globalization pose significant challenges for teachers and learners in the translation field. Resolving these issues requires a comprehensive strategy that includes academic discipline, hands-on training, ethical sensitivity, and a willingness to adjust to the changing global environment.

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